
OUTSOURCING HUMAN RESOURCE FUNCTION AND CORPORATE PERFORMANCE

Victor Barinua (Ph.D)

*Department of Management, Faculty of Management Sciences
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria*

Imaga, Benjamin Ebube

*Department of Management, Faculty of Management Sciences
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria*

ABSTRACT

Performance of corporations is unending quest which all firms strive to achieve in a dynamic workplace. Hence, this study examined how outsourcing human resource functions relate with corporate performance. This was informed in an attempt to see the extent to which outsourcing human resource function relates with the performance of corporate bodies. The desk research method was adopted which covered a detailed literature review on the various variables under study. The study was founded on the resource dependency theory. Recruitment outsourcing and training outsourcing were covered as the dimensions of outsourcing human resource functions while corporate performance was operationalized using firm's productivity and operational efficiency. It was observed from extant literature that outsourcing of human resource function is relevant in enhancing the performance of organizations. The study concluded that human resource outsourcing strategy when properly planned will make organizations focus on their main abilities thereby enhancing productivity by increasing operational efficiency, and profitability, and firm is able to compete favourably with both local and international market without necessarily spending too much in technology and people. The study recommended among others that firms' management should regularly appraise staff performance in order to know when to plan for training outsourcing if need be in order to stimulate employee performance which in turn affects firm productivity.

Key Words: Corporate Performance, Firm Productivity, Operational Efficiency, Outsourcing Human Resource Functions, Recruitment Outsourcing, Training Outsourcing.

Introduction

Recently, the competitive advantage of organisation is facing serious challenge due to the global economic shift. This is reflected in the performances of corporations. Organisational performance according to Farlex (2012), it is the real results an organisation derive when compared to its planned results (aims and goals). Richard et al. (2009) puts that performance of organization include three main outcomes of corporate, they are; financial performance (profits, return on assets, return on investment, etc.); product market performance (sales, market share, etc.); and shareholder return performance (total shareholder return, economic value added, etc.). With resources suitably used organizational will be provided with impeccably outlined goals, objective, and strategies. A thoroughly designed structure will assist organisation to attain higher performance Alzhrani, (2020). The achievement of organization's goal is hinge prominently on conditions such as productivity, cost efficiency and successful strategic human resource management (SHRM).

Organizational performance is veritably considered when owners of firms evaluate both the positive and negative sides of Human resource outsourcing. The function of human resource is a major asset for any organisation that desires increase efficiency and profitability Igbinomwanhia1 (2013). Human resource function is placed with the duty of making sure the needed quality and number of staff are offered when required in the organisation in a given time. Outsourcing human resource is a way to concurrently reduce costs and increase service in today's business environment (Rosenthal, 2002).

By CIPD (2009) definition, human resource outsourcing is buying the services of human resource from a third party supplier that it should have provided by itself. A school of thought is that organizations can concentrate its outlays on improving the goods it sells. Doing this will help organization assign funds to areas that include research and development, instead of employing, maintaining workers and other human resources responsibilities. Another school of thought that concerns itself with human capital and skills, is of the opinion that organization may lack the wherewithal to operate a viable and active human resources department. This condition will need human resource outsourcing to solve the problems organizations may encounter as it hunt for human resources expert that can be fixed into the organisation (Elmuti, 2003).

Human resource outsourcing strategy when properly planned will make organizations focus on their main abilities thereby enhancing productivity without necessarily spending too much in technology and people (King, 2007; Lau & Zhang, 2006). Furthermore this strategy will aid firms to make more profit, and also compete favourably with both local and international market (Maidment, 2003). Considering the benefit of human resource outsourcing (CIPD, 2009; Saha, 2009; Tian, 2007, Nagpal, 2008; Kang and Wu, 2009; Houtzagers and Janssen, 2008) asserts that all industry are limited in resources and manager's time is limited. Outsourcing therefore permits the human resource of organisations to move its concentration from fringe duties to the key operations of the organisation. Also, by outsourcing high spending on non-core function of the organisation is minimized.

Human resource operations is faced with the threat of losing expertise due to the current trend of repeated downsizing, mergers and acquisition and all the fears associated with continuous upgrading of technology. Nonetheless, outsourcing provides organisations with access to human resource proficiency that are not found within and relief the cost of up to date improvement in technology and training.

Several authors have written about outsourcing as a driver of corporate performance. Jirawuttinunt (2015) study is to verify the relationships among human resource outsourcing of four activities. Lilly and Gray (2009) presented a theoretical model that identifies environmental and organizational characteristics that affect human resource (HR) performance in an organization. Igbinomwanhia, et al. (2013) investigated asked if the HR Function is losing its relevance in organizations. Alzhrani (2020) examined outsourcing human resource Functions and their impact on organizational performance. However, there still remains a substantial misperception as to how outsourcing functions of human resources can affect corporate performance in Nigeria. The main aim of this study is therefore to investigate the relationship between outsourcing human resource functions and corporate performance in Rivers state

Statement of the Problem

Every organisation is faced with the challenge of meeting their set goals which is a way of attaining greater performance. The skills and competence features in employees that will help leverage organisation from the menace of economic change is known as human capital. A well-managed human capital is therefore essential organisations to successfully compete and perform exceptionally Lee, (2008). To achieve this, corporations need to put efforts on core duties and assign non-core duties to outsiders. Recently, organizations have outsourced different tasks such as human resource functions in the pursuit of quality service improvement, cost and time reduction increase competence and, to generally spur organizational performance (Munjuri K'Obonyo & Ogutu, 2015).

Notwithstanding the trend toward Human resource outsourcing, proof of its performance results is rare. Opinions for and against outsourcing as a way of attaining competitive advantage have been shared. On one hand some are of the view that organizations may focus more on most value-creating task, as a result become more effective in those task. Also, outsourcing may lead to reduction of cost of training and staffing. On the other hand continuous dependence on outsourcing may lead to reduced innovation (Kotabe, 1992), ultimate unhealthy competition from outsourcing associates (Bettis et al., 1992), and inability to master the task in question. So far, the effect of outsourcing on performance is indeterminate. Moreover, despite several research on this topic, there is lack of in-depth examination of the effect of outsourcing human resource function in Nigeria, in filling this lacuna this work seek to examining the relationship between outsourcing human resource functions and corporate performance.

Conceptual framework

Figure 1: A conceptual Framework for the study.

Source: Adapted from Isaiah (2019)

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between outsourcing human resource functions and corporate performance. The specific objectives are to;

- I. Examine the relationship between recruitment outsourcing and firm productivity.
- II. Determine the relationship between recruitment outsourcing and operational efficiency.
- III. Investigate the relationship between training outsourcing and firm productivity.
- IV. Highlight the relationship between training outsourcing and operational efficiency.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

This segment covers a broad review of works on outsourcing human resource function with its dimensions (recruitment outsourcing and training outsourcing), corporate performance with its measures (firm productivity and goal attainment), pertinent theories and empirical review.

Concept of Outsourcing Human Resource Functions

In a dynamic and competitive global business world, competency is paramount to organizational success. This can be attained when firm concentrates on their primary assignment (Potkány, 2008; Merrifield, 2006; Li-Hua & Simon, 2007; Kirchner, 2006). Appropriate plan and executed approaches to advance performance and change in the perception of employees (Hirshman, Cords, & Hunter, 2005), industrial and economic practices are frequently developing (Kong, 2007). Outsourcing can be viewed as the transfer of a company's non-principal duties to another firm that base on that duty, product or service (Hansen, 2009; Lawler & Mohrman, 2003). Gilley & Rasheed, (2000), sees outsourcing as the purchase of function from outside seller that might have been carried out within. Among others, education, human resource function, hiring and relocation can be outsourced.

One major role of human resource is to make sure appropriate number of employee needed by a firm is gotten where and when required. This role creates a good work atmosphere that enables the organisations and workers ability to be fully utilized Armstrong, (2001). With a healthy relation between organisation and outsourcing company, any human resource function can be outsourced with the access the highest gain. Almost all companies according to investigations, have been proved to have outsourced portion of its HR functions (Gurchiek, 2005). About all these companies still have the intention to further outsource their functions. Belcourt (2006) found that training, salaries, temporary personnel and management are some of the main function HR outsources. He went further to observe that while smaller firms can outsource all HR function some large firms retain critical component of their HR functions. Okeke- Ezeanyanwu (2017) argues that increase in efficiency, returns and the value for firm output is one of the influence of outsourcing on productivity.

Recruitment Outsourcing

Recruitment outsourcing the process of increasing the effectiveness of a firm via giving the functions of recruitment to outside recruiting agencies which have better competitive skills required and saving managerial time. Recruitment outsourcing represent the process of selecting and recruiting employees Duggan and Croy (2004) pointed out some reasons for recruitment outsourcing. They emphasized that acquiring a major personnel is a systematical critical value for firm. Special skills by recruitment outsourcing are required to obtain a highly proficient staff. Also the high cost of hunting, assessing and selecting the most qualified applicant necessitates recruitment outsourcing as mere personnel managers do not possess such talents in picking the staff.

Dasborough and Sue-Chan (2002) put that recruitment outsourcing can be influenced by legislation and industry practices. Factors for decision making when it comes to outsourcing is classified into contextual and organizational factors (Siew-Chen and Vinayan, 2016). Masinovic (2010) reveals another side of recruitment outsourcing. He posits that different organisations' stakeholders are affected as recruitment outsourcing processes affects the self-confidence, commitment and allegiance of employees. More positive result is attained in organizational performance by deciding to adopt recruitment outsourcing strategy in human resource because the vendors have the know-how in recruiting and selecting skilled employees (Cole, 2017). (Siew-Chen and Vinayan, 2016) evaluates the firm's recruitment outsourcing process from beginning to end, in three sections: decision, implementation and outcome.

Training outsourcing

This is when the training firm should provide its employee is outsourced. It is the use of a third party training service. The impact of training on staff is a major area of human resource management. Kooij et al.(2010) argues that the commitment HR practices, which include training and development, is targeted at creating a solid union of affection to the organization, that will bring about enhanced performance and other favourable results. No matter how strong the learning and development aspect of an organisation is, it is almost not possible to achieve the training need of employees in an increasing firm. Outsourcing will be a great relief to this organisational stress (Shih and Chiang, 2011). Training and development outsourcing is seen as an active strategy for management of organisations who operates in a very competitive global business environments. While it has proved that there is increase in the amount of training and development outsourcing (Babcock 2004), firms utilizes their Human resources practices in considerably different ways (Csoko 1995).

Chaudhuri and Bartlett (2014) supported that there is a significant positive relationship between training outsourcing and employee commitment. The choice of training outsourcing in business strategy is due to factors such as the need for quality improvement, reduction of cost and the need for expertise. Outsourcing the training aspect of human resource is strategically vital for the firm, management and training Bansal (2014).Several factors are to be considered when sourcing for a training consultant, most importantly amongst others the need of firm should be considered before embarking on outsourcing project. Outsourcing training service providers becomes more than a vendor, but a true partner when they understands and are interested in unique needs of organisation (Stroh & Treehuboff, 2013).

Concept of Corporate Performance

Continual development is the desire of every organization, it is however imperative to understand that performance of organization correlates with the performance of individual team members in the organization. Performance is the level which organisations attain goals through some means and resources (Horga, 2012). Richard et al. (2009) put that performance of organization include three main outcomes of corporate, they are; financial performance (profits, return on assets, return on investment, etc.); product market performance (sales, market share, etc.); and shareholder return performance (total shareholder return, economic value added, etc.). With resources suitably used organizational will be provided with impeccably outlined goals, objective, and strategies. A thoroughly designed structure will assist organisation to attain higher performance Alzhrani, (2020). The achievement of organization's goal is hinge prominently on conditions such as productivity, cost efficiency and successful strategic human resource management (SHRM).Organizational performance is veritably considered when owners of firms evaluate both the positive and negative sides of Human resource outsourcing. The function of human resource is a major asset for any organisation that desires increase efficiency and profitability Igbinomwanhia1 (2013).

Firm Productivity

Productivity includes the general level of profit, input, employees and total stock needed to create a product. It is the level of outputs and inputs Windrum et al., (2009). Productivity is ability for firm or individual to create demanded product at reduced cost, material, time and energy Shields and Brown, (2015). It is not uncommon that productivity is a major measure of organisational performance but recognizing and exploring the conditions that spur productivity is major issue of concern to every nations economic and even researchers (Armstrong, 2006).

Herti, et al (2011) termed productivity as individual's job realization level having put forth effort. They consider that productivity is an individual occurrence. Nevertheless, some ecological conditions do have noteworthy impact on performance. Some benefits are accrued to organisation when individuals work is determine and evaluated by various attempt Herti, et al (2011). It has been observed that firm success and productivity is majorly relied on the performance of its employees, Armstrong (2002). Nigel (2009) argues that human resource management functions positively and significantly relates with firms productivity. The appraisal of staff performance, training, team work and HR planning all stimulates employee performance which in turn affects firm productivity Nigel (2009). Yu and Linday (2011) posit that the choice to outsource human resource function will make firm productivity to increase as attention marginal duties to customer's need- fulfilling duties.

Operational efficiency

Efficiency according to Mandl et al. (2008) is the connection between inputs and output. Operational efficiency, according to Kovac (2007), is the positive results of the connection between inputs and the outputs. Efficiency is the ability to obtain large output using the least amount of input Robbins and Coulter (2005). Literature has found different methods of measuring operational efficiency. Efficiency cannot be calculated explicitly, rather distinct data methods and computational frameworks are employed. Benchmarking and comparative research, according to Koh and Saad (2007), are widely used approaches. Rolstadas (1995) proposes a comprehensive, iterative method for evaluating and selecting the industry's top organisations.

Financial performance and operational efficiency, according to Venkatraman and Ramanujam (1986), are the most important factors determining a company's effectiveness. While the financial sector looks at things like revenue growth, profitability, and earnings per share, the operational sector looks at things like market share, new product introductions, product quality, and manufacturing value added, among other things. However, there are several different ways to quantify performance.

Empirical review

The objective of Jirawuttinunt (2015) study is to verify the relationships among human resource outsourcing of four activities such as recruitment activities, training administration, payroll management, and human resource information system and organizational performance through HR cost efficiency, effective HR development and HR flexibility. The model is tested by using data collected from mail survey questionnaires of 165 multinational firms and using a questionnaire as the instrument. The results of OLS regression analysis show that HRM outsourcing has a significant impact on organizational performance both direct and indirect via HR cost efficiency, effective HR development and HR flexibility. In sum, this study contributes to manager by providing the knowledge that organizational performance can be increased by HR outsourcing implementation. Theoretical and managerial contributions, conclusion and directions of the future research are mentioned.

The rise of globalization has transformed outsourcing into one of the broadly adopted business plans towards supplying exceptional services to consumers. As can be seen by the ever-increasing trends in outsourcing, the literature on how outsourcing activities affect manufacturing companies' results is insufficient. The research of Alzhrani, (2020) was to investigate the impact on the performance of the outsourcing of human resources functions. Therefore, the results revealed that outsourcing HR functions play an important role in the improvement of organizational performance which can be characterized in three major

dimensions; productivity, profitability, and cost efficiency. This study is limited to literature analysis and in future the three dimensions found by research can be investigated empirically. Policy makers and human resource managers can incorporate the strategies suggested by study to increase the performance of their organization.

Lilly and Gray (2009) presents a theoretical model that identifies environmental and organizational characteristics that affect human resource (HR) performance in an organization. Specifically, we address the issue of when and under what circumstances does HR outsourcing contribute value to the firm by attempting to identify environmental and organizational characteristics that affect HR department performance and how HR outsourcing mediates that relationship. We propose that supplier competition in the HR provider market has a direct effect on the amount of HR outsourcing which in turn has a direct effect on HR performance. Environmental uncertainty (primary, competitive, and supplier) is proposed to moderate the relationship between amount of HR outsourcing and HR performance while asset specificity is proposed to moderate the relationship between supplier competition and amount of HR outsourcing.

Masinovic (2010) examined how RPO affects organisational culture, more precisely three factors were examined, motivation, performance orientation and effective orientation. Five international banks in Sweden were investigated and the results showed that motivation was not affected at all by RPO, effective orientation was affected by the most of the companies studied and the performance orientation was affected by circum one third of the companies by RPO. Human Resource study field has a lack of research in RPO and this study is a contribution to that field, regarding the outsourcing of recruitment in the Swedish bank industry. Bhaker (2020) research on recruitment process outsourcing to establish the current body of knowledge and, on this basis, to identify gaps in our understanding. This action will rationalize future research activities. The study consists of a systematic review of 36 articles which include 21 refereed empirical papers, 3 review papers, 7 conceptual papers, 3 reports and 2 theses on recruitment process outsourcing. Five themes were identified: Recruitment Process Outsourcing (RPO), key motivators of recruitment process outsourcing, benefits and risks of RPO, effects of RPO on different stakeholders and RPO in India. It seems that there is lack of understanding concerning the concept of recruitment process outsourcing.

Due to shortage of research on training outsourcing as a human resource development (HRD) practice and the potential relationships with desired organizational outcomes including employee commitment. Chaudhuri and Bartlett (2014) examined the relationship between training and organizational commitment by focusing exclusively on outsourced training. Data were collected from information technology firms in two countries: India and the United States. Results showed positive relationships between specific measures of employee perceptions of quality, usefulness and supervisor support for outsourced training with organizational commitment. Recommendations are made for future research as well as for professional practice to guide HRD practitioners involved in the rapidly growing global practice of training outsourcing.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Resource dependency Theory (RDT)

Resource dependency Theory (RDT)

Resource dependency theory (RDT) is a theory that tries to explain the behaviour of the organisation and inter-organisation through analysing the critical resources an organisation is

required to have to be able to survive and function (Johnson Jr., 1995). Pfeffer and Salancik's (1978; 2003) view on the theory described that the resources needed from the organisation are dependent on the external sources; the resources needed are financial, physical, and information (Pfeffer & Salancik, 2003; Fink, Edelman, Hatten & James 2006). There are two different theoretical dimensions of resource dependency discovered by Casciaro and Piskorski (2005), power imbalance and mutual dependence. These two dimensions are combined in the original theory, but Casciaro and Piskorski (2005) do not believe in the combined dimension because they have opposite effects on the ability to reduce dependencies of the external sources an organisation has. The resources of a company are areas this dissertation will focus on as well as the human resources. Since the RDT is used to explain the behaviour of the organisation and inter-organisation, it is useful in this type of research where resources are examined. This research is about how the organisational culture is affected when recruiting from recruitment agencies and this theory critically analyses resources, just as this study is analysing RPO.

Gap in Literature

Scholars have examined various ways to address the issue of corporate performance using various constructs. However, there exist dearth of works which have examined how outsourcing human resource functions relates with corporate performance. Given that outsourcing human resource function is of recent origin in human resource management, general understanding is rather limited regarding the motivators, benefits, risks and effects of outsourcing human resource function in organisation. This has created a gap in literature. This study tends to bridge this observed lacuna in literature.

Conclusions

Human resource outsourcing strategy when properly planned will make organizations focus on their main abilities thereby enhancing productivity by increasing operational efficiency, and profitability, and firm is able to compete favourably with both local and international market without necessarily spending too much in technology and people. Considering the benefit of human resource outsourcing and its increasing significance, a better understanding of this topic is essential and can contribute to a better management of the upsides and downsides regarding the different type of outsourcing

Recommendation

1. Firms with outsourcing plan should analyze thoroughly their needs and the benefits and implications of outsourcing, rather than simply jumping on outsourcing human resource functions.
2. Firms management should regularly appraisal staff performance in order to know when to plan for training outsourcing if need be in order to stimulates employee performance which in turn affect firm productivity
3. Owners of firms should evaluate both the positive and negative sides of Human resource outsourcing as it is a factor of corporate performance.
4. Firms should make the outsourcing training service providers to understand and be interested in the unique need of the organisation thereby becoming more than just a vendor, but a true partner of the firm.
5. There should be a healthy relationship between organisations and outsourcing company, this will bring about the highest gain.

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